

FEATURES OF THE TRANSLATION OF ENGLISH NEOLOGISMS IN NEWSPAPER HEADLINES.

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Abstract: The study is devoted to the study of the specifics and practical difficulties in translating English newspaper headlines into Uzbek and Russian. Currently, the problem of translating the headlines of journalistic material is one of the most actively developing in modern linguistics, prompting philologists and journalists to study newspaper headlines.

Key words: journalism, headline functions, linguistics, newspaper headline, pragmatics.

Modern society cannot be imagined without the media. Their role is so great that the media often call it the “fourth estate”.

One of the oldest forms of mass media is the press. It is independent, potentially capable of acting as an independent force. The press occupies an important place in the cultural and political life of the country, helping a person to navigate the surrounding reality.

An integral part of newspaper publications is the headline. A good headline greatly enhances the competitiveness of a periodical. In the press, the headline occupies the strongest position. It is to him that the reader pays attention in the first place. Therefore, the image of a newspaper or magazine largely depends on the nature and design of the headings, as well as the impact of a particular publication on the reader: a meaningful article with an incorrectly chosen heading is not noticed, while even the most mediocre article can gain popularity due to its bright, expressive title. Thus, the title is the organic first element of a text post.

Of great interest is the translation of newspaper headlines. The peculiarities of the development of the press in the UK had a significant impact on the formation of newspaper headlines, the translation of which is often associated with a number of difficulties. To develop a correct understanding and translation of newspaper headlines in the English media, it is not enough to know the theory of translation. For the correct and effective translation of newspaper headlines, it is

necessary to highlight their features, as well as the difficulties that may arise in the translation process.

The purpose of this work is to identify the features of the translation of the headlines of the English press into Russian.

In the explanatory dictionary of T.F. Ephraim title is defined as the title of a work (literary, scientific, musical, etc.) or its individual parts [4]. According to Dahl's dictionary, the heading is the output sheet, the first sheet of a book or essay, where its title is indicated. The title is also called the name of the department, chapter of the book [5].

Both of these definitions are consistent with the newspaper headline. However, it is worth noting that the newspaper headline has a number of features that distinguish it from headlines of other styles, which is associated with its functions.

There are various types of headers. But as diverse as headline models are, they still have a lot in common. Indeed, for the success of the publication, it is necessary that its title meets certain requirements.

Newspaper headlines are written in concise and concise language. But since newspapers are most often aimed at a wide range of readers, any newspaper headline should be easily perceived and read without difficulty. At the same time, the newspaper headline should be expressive enough to grab the reader's attention.

The title should give an idea of the text even before reading it. E.A. Lazareva noted several types of erroneous semantic interaction in the heading-text system:

- a) fuzzy connections between the title and the text;
- b) title ambiguity;
- c) the contradiction between the meaning of the title and the content of the text or between their evaluation [3].

The title should consist mainly of the keywords of the article. Key words should be chosen in such a way that they express the content of the concepts contained in them unambiguously. At the same time, the title should not contain more than 5-6 words, it should not contain complex structures. A short title is better perceived and remembered.

The impact of the headline on the reader to a large extent depends on its technical design (color, location, font, size, etc.)

Now in newspaper speech there is an interaction of book and colloquial versions of the literary language, as well as a strong influence of vernacular and jargon on the language of the media.

Stylistic features of English newspaper headlines and their transmission in translation

You can understand the nature of the English newspaper headline by highlighting its main stylistic features:

1. The use of a regulated set of language tools - lexical units and syntactic structures

This set of language tools is used in order to speed up and simplify the reading of the material as much as possible:

Churches call for end to racial tension

Church calls for an end to racial strife

(For example, clichés, like nothing else, reflect the traditional manner of presenting material in newspaper articles.)

2. The colloquial familiarity of English headlines

For the English reader, such a colloquial-familiar character of headings is the norm and is not striking. However, due to its unusualness, it will make a much greater impression on the Russian reader. Therefore, when translating such headlines, it is necessary to take into account the peculiarities of the Russian newspaper and journalistic style:

EU to slap fresh sanctions on Syria

New EU sanctions on Syria

Say hello to intelligent pills

Developed "intellectual" pill

3. Expressiveness

English headlines are more expressive than Russian ones. Therefore, it is necessary to take into account this expressiveness of lexical and grammatical means and translate English headings so that they are understandable to the Russian reader:

After EU "Yes", Croatia needs reforms, tight budget

Croatia on EU doorstep: reforms needed

(The English newspaper headline is expressive due to its colloquial nature. In order to betray this expressiveness to the Russian headline, the phraseological unit "on the verge of s-l./k-l.")

4. Concise, staccato title rhythm

English titles, due to the desire for brevity and conciseness, have a more compressed, abrupt rhythm than Russian titles:

Russian newspaper headlines tend to be less concise, so in English-Russian translations it is often necessary to choose a longer version:

Obama Drastically Cuts Military; Sparks Heated Debate in Congress

Drastic reduction of the US military forces caused heated debate in Congress

(In this case, the conciseness and brevity of the English title is achieved by omitting the subject.)

The highlighted features characterize in general terms the properties and differences in the style of Russian and English newspaper headlines. Now it is necessary to consider the specific lexical and grammatical features of English newspaper headlines.

5. Multi-stage structure

In English and American newspapers, headlines are often multi-stage (consisting of the heading itself and a subheading). Such headlines are a multi-stage presentation of the main provisions of a newspaper article or newspaper report. This trend is also observed in Russian:

Haas questions future

German considering whether he is able to continue at the top level

Tommy Haas questions the future

German tennis player assesses his chances to continue to be among the best

Lexical features of English newspaper headlines and their transmission in translation

Newspaper headlines are characterized by an abundance of socio-political terms, numerals, neologisms, international words, dialectisms, poeticisms, the translation of which usually does not cause difficulties. We will consider the lexical features of English newspaper headlines, which usually create difficulties in translation.

1. Headline Jargon

In the field of vocabulary, English newspaper headlines are characterized by the frequent use of a small number of special words that make up a kind of “headline jargon”: ban, bid, claim, crack, crash, cut, dash, hit, move, pact, plea, probe, quit, quiz, rap, rush, slash, etc. A distinctive feature of such “heading vocabulary” is not only the frequency of their use, but also the universal nature of their semantics: [1, 120 p.]

Due to the broad semantics of “heading jargon”, it is often necessary to resort to concretization when translating headings:

Russia claims US interest in S. Sudan motivated by oil

Russia believes that US interests in South Sudan are related to oil

(The polysemantic word "to claim" has the following meanings in Russian:

1) demand; make demands;

2) declare, approve;

3) file a claim for damages, etc. In accordance with the content of the article, when translating the verb "to claim" into Russian, the verb "count" is used, which is narrower in meaning.)

India uproar at call in Russia to ban Bhagavad Gita

India outraged by attempt to ban Bhagavad Gita in Russia

(The verb "to ban" means:

1) impose a ban; forbid;

2) deprive the right of use;

3) curse;

4) outlaw, etc.

In this example, it translates as "prohibit".)

2. Phraseologisms, clichés, puns, deliberately modified set expressions, allusions and various set combinations

The task of the translator in this case is connected not only with the recognition of these phenomena in newspaper headlines, but also with the observance of the stylistic and grammatical features of the headings of the target language.

Allusion: Mars attacks! Morocco pelted with rocks from the Red Planet

Mars attacks! Martian meteor shower hits Morocco

(Allusion to Tim Burton's "Mars Attacks!")

Angela Merkel and the euro: the new iron chancellor

Angela Merkel and the euro: Germany's new iron chancellor

(A reference to Federal Chancellor Otto von Bismarck.)

Thus, in this paper, only the most important features of English newspaper headlines, which are directly related to the problem of their understanding and translation into Russian, were considered. There are no specific rules for translating newspaper headlines, but knowing their main features and having extensive background knowledge, the translator is able to perform an adequate translation of headlines.

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